

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DESTINATION CHOICE OF DOMESTIC TOURISTS TO HANOI

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Abstract

In order to investigate the factors influencing domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi as a destination, the research team surveyed 294 tourists visiting Hanoi and processed the collected survey data using SMARTPLS software. The research findings indicate that among the seven factors examined, six have statistically significant effects while one does not reach statistical significance to draw a conclusion. Notably, the factor Travel Cost (CP) exerts the strongest influence on domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi as a destination, with an effect size of 0.241; followed by Destination Image (HA) and Perceived Information (NT), with effect sizes of 0.201 and 0.169, respectively. Meanwhile, the factor Tourists' Previous Experience (TN) does not show sufficient statistical significance to conclude its effect on the decision to choose Hanoi as a destination. Based on the analysis results, the research team proposes several solutions to attract tourists to choose Hanoi as their destination.

Keywords: Domestic Tourists; Hanoi Destination; Influencing Factors; Destination Choice Decision.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hanoi, the thousand-year-old capital, is a convergence of distinctive historical, cultural, culinary, and scenic values, possessing tremendous potential to become a premier destination for domestic tourists. However, in reality, the growth rate of domestic tourist arrivals to Hanoi has not yet fully matched its inherent potential.

This situation underscores the urgent need to thoroughly understand tourist behavior and the factors influencing domestic tourists' destination choice decisions, thereby formulating appropriate solutions to attract visitors and enhance the competitiveness of the capital's tourism industry. This study aims to examine the factors affecting domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi as their destination.

Using desk research, the research team reviewed relevant concepts and theoretical foundations related to tourist motivation, attitude, and travel decision-making. Subsequently, a sociological survey was conducted by designing a questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale using Google Forms. The questionnaire was distributed directly at tourist sites or sent online via the link: <https://forms.gle/Zdoa2JZ2jmtNKL1i6> through

tourism enterprises. A total of 298 responses were collected, of which 4 were incomplete and excluded. The remaining 294 valid responses formed the dataset for analysis.

The factors examined in their impact on domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi include: *Tourism Motivation, Positive Attitude, Perceived Behavioral Control, Destination Image, Perceived Information, Travel Cost, and Previous Experience.*

The survey data were validated and analyzed using SmartPLS software, thereby assessing the influence level of each factor on domestic tourists' destination choice decision regarding Hanoi. Based on the analysis results, the research team proposes a number of discussions and suggestions to attract tourists to choose Hanoi as their destination.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, RESEARCH MODEL, AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Tourism and Tourism Destination

Tourism refers to activities related to a person's travel outside their usual place of residence for a continuous period not exceeding one year, undertaken to satisfy the need for sightseeing, relaxation, entertainment, exploration of tourism resources, or combined with other lawful purposes (Vietnam Tourism Law, 2017).

A tourist is defined as a person traveling for tourism purposes or combining tourism with other activities, excluding those traveling for study or employment to earn income at the destination. Accordingly, tourists include: domestic tourists, inbound international tourists, and outbound tourists (Vietnam Tourism Law, 2017).

A trip may be organized by an individual, a group such as a community, friends, colleagues, agencies, or organizations. A tourism destination is defined as a physical space where visitors stay for at least one night, encompassing tourism products and services such as attractions, accommodation, dining, entertainment, and transport connections.

According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), *"A local tourism destination is a physical space in which a visitor spends at least one overnight. It includes tourism products such as support services and attractions, and tourism resources within one day's return travel time. It has physical and administrative boundaries defining its management, images and perceptions determining its market competitiveness."*

2.2. Some Research Models on Behavioral Intention

2.2.1. Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) was developed by Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975. According to this model, behavioral intention leads to behavior, and intention is determined by the individual's attitude toward the behavior, along with the influence of subjective norms regarding the performance of that behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975).

Figure 1: The Theory of Reasoned Action – TRA

Source: Fishbein và Ajzen (1975)

- (1) *Consumers' attitude toward the behavior.* An individual's attitude is measured by the consumer's beliefs and evaluations of the outcomes of that behavior. When consumers have confidence in a product, they tend to be more inclined to develop the intention to use the firm's product.
- (2) *Consumers' subjective norms.* Consumers are influenced by the attitudes of significant others, such as friends and family members, toward the use of the product, as well as by the consumer's motivation to perform the behavior in accordance with the expectations of those significant others.

2.2.2. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior was developed by Ajzen (1991) as an extension of the original TRA, incorporating the additional factor of *perceived behavioral control*, alongside *attitude* and *subjective norms*, to explain consumers' behavioral intentions. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is a model that explains human behavior based on individuals' intentions to perform a specific action. The TPB posits that a person's intention to perform a behavior is influenced by three main factors: *Attitude*, *Subjective Norms*, and *Perceived Behavioral Control*. These factors interact with each other and jointly predict an individual's intention to carry out the behavior, which in turn directly influences actual behavior. The TPB provides a clearer understanding of the mechanisms through which psychological and social factors affect human behavior.

Figure 2: The theoretical model of planned behavior – TPB

Source: Ajzen, 1991

Attitude toward a behavior can be understood as an individual's feelings toward a product or service and their evaluation of that behavior, which can be positive or negative, but is based on their perception of the expected outcomes.

Subjective norms refer to an individual's perception of social pressure to perform a behavior. This relates to the extent to which they perceive pressure from those around them and their awareness of societal approval or disapproval.

Perceived behavioral control encompasses both self-control and self-awareness. Self-control relates to an individual's belief about external factors that may influence their behavior, while self-awareness reflects their evaluation of their own ability to perform the behavior.

2.3. Proposed Research Model and Hypotheses

Based on previous studies and the theoretical framework, and grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research team proposes the following research model:

Figure 3: Proposed Research Model

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis H1: *“Tourism motivation” has a positive influence on the decision to choose Hanoi as a destination.*

Hypothesis H2: *“Behavioral Attitude” has a positive influence on the destination choice decision.*

Hypothesis H3: *“Perceived behavioral control” has a positive influence on the destination choice decision.*

Hypothesis H4: *“Destination image” has a positive influence on tourists’ choice decision.*

Hypothesis H5: *“Perceived Information” has a positive influence on tourists’ destination choice decision.*

Hypothesis H6: *“Travel cost” has a negative influence on the decision to choose Hanoi as a destination.*

Hypothesis H7: *“Previous experience” has a positive influence on the intention to return and continue choosing the destination.*

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on the theoretical framework and literature review of factors influencing tourist destination choice behavior, the independent variables incorporated into the research model include: *“Tourism motivation”, “Behavioral Attitude”, “Perceived behavioral control”, “Destination image”, “Perceived Information”, “Travel cost”, and “Previous experience”*

The questionnaire was designed using a five-point Likert scale with the following indicators: *1. Strongly disagree; 2. Disagree; 3. Neutral; 4. Agree; 5. Strongly agree.*

After drafting the questionnaire, the research team conducted a pilot survey with a small group of domestic tourists who had previously visited Hanoi, in order to assess the clarity, comprehensibility, and appropriateness of the questions. The pilot results indicated that the questionnaire items were reasonable, contextually appropriate, and effectively measured the proposed theoretical constructs.

Due to time and resource constraints, the research team employed a convenience sampling method to collect primary data. The sample size was determined based on the recommendation of Comrey and Lee (1992) and the standard suggested by Hoàng Trọng and Chu Nguyễn Mộng Ngọc (2005), which requires at least five observations per observed variable in the model. With a total of 38 observed variables, the minimum required sample size was $38 \times 5 = 190$ observations. However, to ensure the representativeness and reliability of the analysis results, the research team decided to distribute a total of 300 questionnaires.

The survey respondents were domestic tourists visiting attractions in the inner districts of Hanoi. The questionnaires were distributed via two channels: directly at tourist sites and online through Google Forms using the link: <https://forms.gle/Zdoa2JZ2jmtNKL1i6>, with support from several local travel agencies.

In total, 298 responses were collected. After reviewing and cleaning the data, 4 invalid responses due to missing critical information were excluded. The remaining 294 valid responses were used as the official dataset for subsequent data processing and model testing.

3.2. Data Processing Method

SMARTPLS software was employed to test the research hypotheses and assess the impact levels of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluating Measurement Model

Evaluating measurement model based on examining values of reliability, quality of observed variable, convergence, and discriminant

- Testing the quality of observed variables (Outer Loadings)

Outer Loadings of observed variables are indicators showing the degree of association between observed variables and latent variables (proxy variables). Basically, outer loadings in SMARTPLS are the square root of the absolute value of R² linear regression from the latent variables to the sub-observed variables.

Hair et al. (2016) suggest that the outer loadings should be greater than or equal to 0.708 observed variables that are quality. To make it easier to remember, the researchers rounded off the threshold to 0.7 instead of the number 0.708.

- Evaluating Reliability

Evaluating the reliability through SMARTPLS by two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Composite Reliability (CR) is preferred by many researchers over Cronbach's Alpha because Cronbach's Alpha underestimates the reliability compared with CR. Chin (1998) claims that in exploratory research CR must be over 0.6. For confirmed studies, the 0.7 threshold is the appropriate level of CR (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013). Other researchers agree that 0.7 is the appropriate threshold for the vast majority of cases such as Hair et al. (2010), and Bagozzi & Yi (1988).

Thus, the reliability through SMARTPLS is shown by Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012); Composite Reliability CR ≥ 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988).

- Testing Convergence

Evaluating Convergence on SMARTPLS is based on Ave (Average Variance Extracted). Hock & Ringle (2010) claim that a scale reaches a convergence value if AVE reaches 0.5 or higher. This level of 0.5 (50%) means that the average latent variable will explain at least 50% of the variation of each sub-observed variable. Thus, convergence is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted AVE ≥ 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010).

- Testing Discriminant Validity

Discriminant value is used to consider whether a research variable is really different from other research variables in the model. To evaluate the discriminant validity, Sarstedt & et al (2014) said that considering two criteria including cross-loadings and the measurement of Fornell and Larcker (1981).

Cross-loading coefficients are often the first approach to evaluating the discriminant validity of indicators (observed variables) (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017). The load factor of the observed variable (indicator) linked in the factor (latent variable) should be greater than any of its cross-load factors (its correlation) in the other factors.

Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminant is ensured when the square root of AVE for each latent variable is higher than all correlations between latent variables. In

addition, Henseler & et al (2015) used simulation studies to demonstrate that discriminant validity is better evaluated by the HTMT index that they developed.

With the HTMT index, Garson (2016) said that the discriminant validity between two latent variables is guaranteed when the HTMT index is less than 1. Henseler & et al (2015) propose that if this value is below 0.9, the discriminant validity will be guaranteed. Meanwhile, Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015) used a stricter standard threshold of 0.85. SMARTPLS preferred a threshold of 0.85 in the evaluation.

- Testing Multicollinearity

In this study, the author uses a scale related to multicollinearity as a variance magnification factor (VIF). Very high levels of multicollinearity are indicated by VIF values ≥ 5 ; the model does not have multicollinearity when VIF indicators < 5 (Hair et al., 2016).

Step 2: Evaluating Structural Model

After evaluating the satisfactory measurement model, evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, R squared, and f squared.

- Evaluating impactful relationships

To evaluate impact relationships, use the results of Bootstrap analysis. Based mainly on two columns (1) Original Sample (normalized impact factor) and (2) P Values (sig value compared to 0.05 significance level).

- Original Sample: Standardized impact factor of the original data. SMARTPLS have no unstandardized impact factor.
- Sample Mean: The average standardized impact factor of all samples from Bootstrap.
- Standard Deviation: Standard deviation of the standardized impact factor (according to the original sample).
- T Statistics: Test value t (test student the meaning of the impact).
- P Values: The significance level of the T Statistics. This significance level is considered with comparative thresholds such as 0.05, 0.1, or 0.01 (usually used as 0.05).

Evaluating the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable by R^2 coefficient (R square). To evaluate the R^2 coefficient, we will use the results of the PLS Algorithm analysis. The R^2 value evaluates the predictive accuracy of the model and shows the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R square is between 0 and 1, the closer to 1 indicates the more independent variables that account for the dependent variable (Hair, Hult, et al, 2017).

Additionally, to evaluate the impact level of each factor, the research team calculated the range and mean value of each factor, and determined which response category the mean score fell into.

The range was computed as:

$$\text{Range} = (\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}) / n = (5 - 1) / 5 = 0.8$$

The assessment thresholds based on the mean score were defined as follows:

- 1.00 – 1.80: *Strongly disagree*
- 1.81 – 2.60: *Disagree*
- 2.61 – 3.40: *Neutral*
- 3.41 – 4.20: *Agree*
- 4.21 – 5.00: *Strongly agree*

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1. Description of the Research Sample

A total of 294 valid responses were collected from domestic tourists participating in the survey on factors influencing the decision to choose Hanoi as a destination. Female respondents accounted for the majority, with 232 individuals (78.9%), while male respondents comprised only 62 individuals (21.1%). Since the survey was conducted using a random sampling method, the higher level of interest and willingness among female tourists to complete the questionnaire resulted in a gender imbalance among the respondents (*Figure 4*)

Figure 4: Gender of survey participants

Source: Survey results

Regarding tourists' age, the research focused on domestic tourists who have traveled or are traveling to Hanoi. Among the 294 respondents, the age group *18–25 years* overwhelmingly dominated, with 239 individuals accounting for 81.3%. The remaining age groups had significantly lower proportions: *26–35 years* accounted for 6.1%, *36–45 years* for 5.4%, and *over 45 years* for 4.8%. The group *under 18 years* represented only 2.4% of the total sample (see *Figure 5*).

Figure 5: Age of tourists participating in the survey

Source: Survey results

Among the 294 survey participants, 39.5% (equivalent to 116 individuals) had never traveled to Hanoi, and 38.4% (equivalent to 113 individuals) had visited Hanoi only once. The proportions of those who had visited Hanoi multiple times were lower: 15.0% had visited 2–3 times, 4.4% had visited 4–5 times, and only 2.7% had visited more than 5 times (see Figure 6)

Figure 6: Number of trips made by tourists

Source: Survey results

The most common length of stay for domestic tourists in Hanoi was 1–2 days, accounting for 45.2% of the 294 survey participants. This was followed by the group staying 3–4 days at 28.9%, and the group staying less than 1 day at 9.9%. Additionally, 4.1% of respondents reported staying 5–7 days, while 11.9% stayed in Hanoi for more than 7 days (see Figure 7)

Figure 7: Length of stay in Hanoi of tourists participating in the survey

Source: Survey results

4.2. Hypothesis Testing Results

4.2.1. Evaluation of the Quality of Observed Variables in the Measurement Model

4.2.1.1. Assessment of Observed Variable Quality

The quality of the observed variables was evaluated through the *outer loadings*. The quality of the observed variables influencing domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi as a destination is presented in *Table 1*.

Table 1: Outer Loadings of Factors Influencing Domestic Tourists' Decision to Choose Hanoi as a Destination

	CP	DC	HA	KS	NT	QD	TD	TN
CP1	0,847							
CP2	0,799							
CP3	0,812							
CP4	0,778							
CP5	0,841							
DC1		0,763						
DC2		0,794						
DC3		0,775						
DC4		0,761						
DC5		0,762						
HA1			0,848					
HA2			0,833					
HA3			0,813					
HA4			0,789					
HA5			0,849					
KS1				0,800				
KS2				0,730				
KS3				0,789				
KS4				0,766				

KS5				0,755				
NT1					0,763			
NT2					0,801			
NT3					0,810			
NT4					0,781			
NT5					0,830			
QD1						0,832		
QD2						0,833		
QD3						0,802		
QD4						0,827		
QD5						0,799		
TD2							0,810	
TD3							0,766	
TD4							0,832	
TN1								0,820
TN2								0,826
TN3								0,814
TN4								0,848
TN5								0,827

Source: Test results using SmartPLS

The results in *Table 1* show that the outer loadings of all observed variables influencing domestic tourists’ decision to choose Hanoi as a destination are greater than 0.7, in line with the threshold suggested by Hair et al. (2016), indicating that the observed variables are statistically significant.

4.2.1.2. Reliability Testing of the Measurement Scales

The reliability of the measurement scales for the factors influencing domestic tourists’ decision to choose Hanoi as a destination was assessed in PLS-SEM using two main indicators: *Cronbach’s Alpha* and *Composite Reliability (CR)*.

Table 2: Reliability Coefficients (Cronbach’s Alpha) and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
CP	0,874	0,875	0,909	0,665
DC	0,830	0,837	0,880	0,594
HA	0,886	0,904	0,915	0,684
KS	0,829	0,850	0,878	0,590
NT	0,857	0,862	0,897	0,636
QD	0,877	0,879	0,910	0,671
TD	0,727	0,740	0,845	0,645
TN	0,885	0,892	0,915	0,684

Source: Test results by the research team

The data in *Table 2* show that the reliability analysis using Cronbach’s Alpha produced the following results: the factor “*Previous travel experience*” (TN) had the highest reliability with an Alpha of 0.885, while the lowest was for “*Positive attitude toward Hanoi as a destination*” (TD) with an Alpha of 0.727. The other factors— “*Travel cost*” (CP), “*Tourism*

motivation” (DC), “Destination image” (HA), “Perceived behavioral control” (KS), “Level of perceived information” (NT), and “Destination choice decision” (QD)—had Alpha values of 0.874, 0.830, 0.886, 0.829, 0.857, and 0.877, respectively.

Thus, all measurement scales satisfied the condition of > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and did not violate any rule requiring variable elimination.

Therefore, no variable was excluded, and the scales are considered acceptable in terms of reliability.

The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables also exceeded 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). Accordingly, the scales demonstrate adequate reliability, are analytically meaningful, and are retained for subsequent factor analysis.

4.2.1.3. Convergent Validity

According to the data analysis results in Table 2, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all variables exceeds 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), indicating that the model satisfies the conditions for convergent validity.

4.2.1.4. Discriminant Validity and Multicollinearity Assessment

The results in Table 3 show the Fornell–Larcker criterion for the research model on factors influencing domestic tourists’ decision to choose Hanoi as a destination.

The factors included in the model all satisfy the condition of discriminant validity, as all square root values on the main diagonal are greater than the off-diagonal correlation values.

Thus, the Fornell–Larcker test results indicate that all scales in the model achieve discriminant validity, ensuring that the theoretical constructs are clearly measured without overlap or content interference.

Table 3: Fornell–Larcker Criterion of the Research Model on Factors Influencing Domestic Tourists’ Decision to Choose Hanoi as a Destination

	CP	DC	HA	KS	NT	QD	TD	TN
CP	0.816							
DC	0.240	0.771						
HA	0.283	0.040	0.827					
KS	0.381	0.070	0.282	0.768				
NT	0.333	0.061	0.118	0.201	0.797			
QD	0.539	0.275	0.382	0.375	0.367	0.819		
TD	0.293	0.235	0.113	0.178	0.083	0.341	0.803	
TN	0.465	0.043	0.283	0.263	0.392	0.422	0.164	0.827

Source: Test results using SmartPLS

Multicollinearity Assessment

The test results presented in Table 4 show that the Inner VIF values, which assess multicollinearity among the latent variables, are all below 3. This indicates that no multicollinearity is present in the model.

Table 4: Multicollinearity/Collinearity Model

	VIF
CP -> QD	1.599
DC -> QD	1.105
HA -> QD	1.163
KS -> QD	1.235
NT -> QD	1.230
TD -> QD	1.140
TN -> QD	1.447

Source: Test results using SmartPLS

4.2.2. Results of Impact Assessment Using the Structural Model

4.2.2.1. Assessment of Influential Relationships

The relationships and impact levels of the factors influencing domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi as a destination, as analyzed in SMARTPLS, are illustrated in *Figure 8*.

Figure 8: Factors Influencing Domestic Tourists' Decision to Choose Hanoi as a Destination

Source: Test results using SMARTPLS by the research team

The results of the *Bootstrap analysis* assessing the influential relationships are presented in *Table 5*. Among the 7 independent factors included in the model, 6 were found to have a positive and statistically significant effect on *Destination Choice Decision (QD)*. Specifically:

Tourism Motivation (DC) shows a significant impact with $\beta = 0.148$, $T = 4.105$, $p = 0.000$, highlighting the important role of personal goals and experiential needs in destination choice behavior. Hypothesis H1 is accepted.

Positive Attitude toward the Destination (TD) also has a significant effect with $\beta = 0.157$, $T = 2.689$, $p = 0.007$, reflecting the role of subjective beliefs and evaluations in decision-making. Hypothesis H2 is accepted.

Perceived Behavioral Control (KS) has a more moderate effect, with $\beta = 0.122$, $T = 2.374$, $p = 0.018$, indicating that factors such as finances, time, and health also influence travel decisions. Hypothesis H3 is accepted. *Destination Image (HA)* exhibits a strong positive effect, with $\beta = 0.201$, $T = 4.816$, $p = 0.000$, demonstrating the importance of tourists' impressions and perceptions of Hanoi. Hypothesis H4 is accepted.

Perceived Information (NT) has $\beta = 0.169$, $T = 5.283$, $p = 0.000$, confirming that access to tourism information plays a critical role in choice behavior. Hypothesis H5 is accepted.

Travel Cost (CP) positively influences the destination choice decision, with $\beta = 0.241$, $T = 2.838$, $p = 0.005$. Hypothesis H6 is accepted.

Conversely, the factor *Previous Travel Experience (TN)* does not reach statistical significance, with $T = 1.655$ and $p = 0.098 > 0.05$. This suggests that prior travel experience in Hanoi is not sufficient to exert a significant impact on the continued choice of the destination, or it may reflect divergent perceptions among different tourist groups. Hypothesis H7 is rejected.

Table 5: Path Coefficients of the Structural Model

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CP -> QD	0.241	0.259	0.085	2.838	0.005
DC -> QD	0.148	0.152	0.036	4.105	0.000
HA -> QD	0.201	0.198	0.042	4.816	0.000
KS -> QD	0.122	0.123	0.051	2.374	0.018
NT -> QD	0.169	0.167	0.032	5.283	0.000
TD -> QD	0.157	0.156	0.058	2.689	0.007
TN -> QD	0.122	0.123	0.074	1.655	0.098

Source: Test results using SMARTPLS by the research team

The test results in *Table 5* indicate that, at a 95% confidence level, the factor "*Travel Cost*" (*CP*) has the strongest impact on domestic tourists' decision to choose Hanoi as a destination, with an influence level of *0.241*. This is followed by "*Destination Image*" (*HA*) at *0.201*, "*Perceived Information*" (*NT*) at *0.169*, "*Positive Attitude toward the Destination*"

(TD) at 0.157, “Tourism Motivation” (DC) at 0.148, and “Perceived Behavioral Control” (KS) at 0.122.

Based on the test results, the regression equation is expressed as follows:

$$QD = 0.241 \cdot CP + 0.201 \cdot HA + 0.169 \cdot NT + 0.157 \cdot TD + 0.148 \cdot DC + 0.122 \cdot KS$$

4.2.2.2. Assessment of the Overall R² Coefficient

The *PLS Algorithm* analysis produced the *R² value*, which reflects the explanatory power of the independent variables on the dependent variable in the model. The *R² coefficient* (R-square value) measures the overall goodness of fit, indicating the model’s explanatory capability. According to Hair et al. (2010), *R² values* are categorized as follows: 0.75: substantial explanatory power, 0.50: moderate explanatory power, and 0.25: weak explanatory power

Table 6: Summary of R² Values

	R-square	R-square adjusted
QD	0.460	0.447

Source: Test results by the research team

The data in *Table 6* show that the adjusted *R²* for the representative factor “*Domestic tourists’ decision to choose Hanoi as a destination*” is 0.447, indicating that the model has a moderate level of explanatory power. This means that 44.7% of the variance in the decision to choose Hanoi as a destination can be explained by the independent variables in the model, while the remaining 55.3% is attributable to systematic error and other factors outside the model.

4.2.3. Descriptive Statistics Results

Figure 9: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Tourism Motivation for Hanoi” (DC)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The survey results show that the highest-rated observed variable is “*I choose Hanoi to explore its unique culture and history*” (DC3), with a mean score of 4.29, indicating strong interest among domestic tourists in the cultural–historical aspects of Hanoi. Other motivations, such as “*I choose Hanoi to discover and experience new things*” (DC2) and “*I choose Hanoi to be closer to nature*” (DC4), both have mean scores of 4.28, while “*I*

choose Hanoi for entertainment and relaxation” (DC1) scores 4.27, and “I choose Hanoi to meet local people and expand social relationships” (DC5) scores 4.26. These findings suggest that Hanoi appeals to tourists not only for its cultural depth but also for its ability to meet a variety of travel purposes.

Figure 10: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Attitude toward Traveling to Hanoi” (TD)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The survey results indicate that all observed variables have high mean scores, ranging from 4.25 to 4.31, demonstrating that the majority of respondents hold a clearly positive attitude toward Hanoi as a tourist destination. The highest mean score is observed for the statement “I believe that Hanoi is a very good and worthwhile tourist destination” (TD1), with a mean of 4.31. Other statements, such as “I feel that Hanoi is a friendly and hospitable destination” (TD2), “I find Hanoi to be an interesting destination with much to explore” (TD3), and “I believe that traveling to Hanoi is a civilized and responsible behavior” (TD4), have mean scores of 4.25, 4.30, and 4.30, respectively, reflecting high and consistent levels of agreement among the respondents.

Figure 11: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Perceived Behavioral Control over Traveling to Hanoi” (KS)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The observed variables for this factor all show high mean scores. The highest mean score is for the statement “I find it easy to search for and access the necessary information for my trip to Hanoi” (KS4), with a mean of 4.30, reflecting the relatively convenient access to tourism information for visitors. Other factors—such as financial capability (KS1), time to arrange the trip (KS2), health condition (KS3), and travel procedures (KS5)—also received high mean scores of 4.24, 4.25, 4.23, and 4.20, respectively, indicating

consistency in respondents' perceptions. These results reflect a positive perception and the proactive attitude of domestic tourists in managing their personal resources when choosing Hanoi as a travel destination.

Figure 12: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Hanoi’s Destination Image” (HA)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

Figure 12 presents the descriptive statistics of the observed variables under the factor “Hanoi’s Destination Image.” The mean values range from 4.11 to 4.17, indicating that domestic tourists hold positive evaluations of Hanoi’s overall image. The highest-rated variable is “Hanoi is a safe destination with stable social security” (HA5), followed by “Hanoi people are friendly and hospitable” (HA4), “Rich and diverse cuisine” (HA2), “Quality of accommodation and transportation services” (HA3), and “Distinctive natural landscapes, historical and cultural relics” (HA1). These results suggest that Hanoi’s image is positively perceived by tourists in terms of security, people, culture, and services.

Figure 13: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Level of Perceived Information about Hanoi” (NT)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

Figure 13 presents the mean values of the measurement scale for the factor “Level of Perceived Information about Hanoi.” The mean scores range from 4.14 to 4.24, indicating that domestic tourists have a relatively high level of access to information about Hanoi tourism. The most accessed source of information is *word of mouth*, specifically recommendations or reviews from friends, colleagues, and family (NT4), highlighting the prominent role of social factors in shaping awareness. Other highly rated channels include: travel companies or agencies (NT5), social media (NT2), and mass media such

as newspapers and television (NT1). Although it has the lowest mean value, *advertising or tourism promotion campaigns (NT3)* is still rated at a fairly good level. These findings suggest that tourists access information about Hanoi from multiple sources, with personal and social factors being more dominant than official media channels.

Figure 14: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Travel Cost in Hanoi” (CP)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The survey results show that nearly all factors have mean values ranging from 4.24 to 4.30, indicating that the majority of respondents agree that the costs associated with traveling to Hanoi are reasonable and within their personal budgets. Among these, the most reasonably rated cost is *transportation to and within Hanoi (CP5)*, with a mean score of 4.30. This is followed by *food and beverage service prices (CP3)*, *entrance and entertainment fees (CP4)*, *overall trip cost (CP1)*, and *accommodation service prices (CP2)*, with mean scores of 4.29, 4.25, 4.26, and 4.24, respectively. Thus, it can be concluded that cost is not a major barrier to the decision to choose Hanoi as a travel destination.

Figure 15: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Previous Travel Experience in Hanoi” (TN)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The survey results show that mean values range from 4.15 to 4.23, reflecting positive evaluations by domestic tourists of their past experiences in Hanoi. The highest-rated item is *“I have learned many new and interesting things from my previous trips to Hanoi” (TN3)*, with a mean score of 4.23. This is followed by *satisfaction with service quality*

(TN2) at 4.18 and *positive and memorable feelings about previous travel experiences* (TN1) at 4.16. The remaining two items—*intention to return to Hanoi* (TN4) and *willingness to recommend to others* (TN5)—both have mean scores of 4.15. These results suggest that previous travel experience is a factor that influences the decision and behavior to revisit Hanoi. However, in this study, the statistical testing results were not strong enough to confirm this relationship, which may be due to the sample’s characteristics, as it mainly consisted of young tourists with limited actual experience in Hanoi.

Figure 16: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Dependent Factor “Decision to Choose Hanoi as a Destination” (QD)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The analysis results show that the mean values of the variables all fall within the range of 4.24 to 4.32, indicating that domestic tourists tend to highly evaluate and express satisfaction with their decision to choose Hanoi as a travel destination.

Notably, the statement “*I will stick to my decision to choose Hanoi even when there are alternative destinations*” (QD3) has the highest mean score of 4.32, reflecting strong consistency and high commitment in tourists’ destination choice decision. In addition, other statements such as “*I carefully considered before making the decision*” (QD1) with a mean of 4.29, and “*I am completely satisfied with my decision to choose Hanoi as my travel destination*” (QD4) with 4.25, as well as “*I believe my decision to choose Hanoi as a travel destination is entirely correct*” (QD2) and “*I will continue to choose Hanoi for future trips*” (QD5) both at 4.24, further support this finding.

These results affirm that Hanoi is a sustainably attractive and reliable choice for domestic tourists.

5. DISCUSSIONS

The structural model test using SmartPLS 4.0 shows that out of the seven proposed hypotheses, six are accepted at a 95% confidence level. Specifically, the factor “Travel Cost” (CP) has the strongest impact on domestic tourists’ decision to choose Hanoi as a destination, with a coefficient of $\beta = 0.241$, reflecting a price-sensitive mindset, particularly among younger, student, and middle-to-low-income groups. Costs related to accommodation, transportation, and entrance fees are regarded as crucial factors directly influencing destination choice. The factor “Destination Image” (HA), with $\beta = 0.201$, also

exerts a significant influence, underscoring the importance of safety, friendliness, service quality, and cultural–historical values in shaping positive tourist impressions. The factors “Perceived Information” ($\beta = 0.169$), “Positive Attitude” ($\beta = 0.157$), “Tourism Motivation” ($\beta = 0.148$), and “Perceived Behavioral Control” ($\beta = 0.122$) are all statistically significant, highlighting the roles of accessible information, favorable attitudes, desire to explore, and personal conditions in travel decisions. In contrast, “Previous Travel Experience” did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.098 > 0.05$), suggesting that past experiences in Hanoi have not yet significantly influenced revisit behavior among the predominantly young sample, who may have limited practical experience in the city. Based on these findings, the research team proposes several recommendations to enhance Hanoi’s tourism competitiveness:

First, optimize travel costs by ensuring price transparency, developing budget-friendly combo packages, and offering targeted promotions based on customer segments and timing

Second, develop tourism products aligned with personal motivations, such as old quarter tours, craft village visits, culinary tours, night tours, and personalized packages based on age and lifestyle.

Third, enhance destination image through investments in tourism infrastructure, restoration of historical sites, improvement of service quality, and promotion of a friendly local image.

Fourth, strengthen tourism information provision and communication via digital platforms, social media, smart apps, QR codes at sites, and partnerships with KOLs and bloggers to expand reach.

Fifth, improve tourists’ perceived control by offering flexible itineraries, convenient booking apps, and support services for seniors and people with disabilities.

Sixth, reinforce positive attitudes toward Hanoi with a consistent branding strategy, promoting its distinctive cultural message and the image of an elegant, peaceful, and hospitable city.

Seventh, improve actual experiences to boost revisit intentions and word-of-mouth promotion through standardized services, satisfaction surveys, loyalty programs, and incentives for sharing experiences on social media.

These solutions not only contribute to attracting domestic tourists but also lay a strong foundation for Hanoi to develop as an attractive, friendly, and sustainable tourism destination in the future.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examines seven independent factors influencing domestic tourists’ decision to choose Hanoi as a destination. The analysis reveals that six factors—*Travel Cost*, *Tourism Motivation*, *Destination Image*, *Perceived Behavioral Control*, *Perceived Information*, and *Positive Attitude toward Hanoi*—are significantly related to the *Decision*

to Choose Hanoi. Among these, *Travel Cost* exerts the strongest influence. The factor *Previous Travel Experience* did not reach statistical significance, possibly due to the sample being predominantly young tourists with limited practical experience in Hanoi. This suggests that future studies should broaden the scope and incorporate qualitative methods. Based on the findings, the authors propose several solutions to attract more domestic tourists to Hanoi in the coming period.

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